

MODERN METHODS OF PREVENTION OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS

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Complications: Congenital heart defects are anatomical defects of the heart, its valvular apparatus, and/or blood vessels originating from the heart that occur in utero (before the child is born). These defects can appear alone or in combination with each other. They manifest themselves as openings ("windows") between the left and right chambers of the heart ("windows" are part of the fetal circulatory system and must be closed after birth), blood in the bloodstream to the lungs as narrowing of the veins. and organs of the body, as well as a violation of the normal flow of blood due to anatomical defects of the heart valve apparatus. Congenital heart defects are one of the most common intrauterine anomalies in children (about 30% of all birth defects). In terms of frequency, it ranks third after congenital pathologies of the musculoskeletal system and central nervous system. Congenital heart defects are detected in 6-8 out of 1000 births.

Research materials and methods: Patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) is a vessel in which the pathological connection between the aorta and the pulmonary artery remains after birth. Later, it is gradually destroyed and turns into an arterial ligament. Usually, the obliteration of the canal ends in 2-8 weeks. Failure to close the channel leads to the formation of heart diseases. If (according to clinical data) it works 1-2 weeks after birth, the ductus arteriosus is considered an anomaly.

Purpose of research: Tetralogy of Fallot (the most common "blue" defect, "blue baby") is a combination of 4 signs: stenosis (narrowing) of the pulmonary artery lumen until it is completely closed, dextroposition of the aorta (displacement of the aorta). right), ventricular septal defect and right ventricular hypertrophy (enlargement) It is accompanied by constant cyanosis from early childhood. Shortness of breath appears from childhood, is associated with even light physical activity, and sometimes has the character of suffocation. Children often seek relief in a reclined position, tend to sit with their legs tucked under them, and sleep with their knees drawn to their stomachs. Fainting and convulsions are common.

Observed results: Changes in atmospheric conditions, excessive heat, cold - shortness of breath, general weakness and increased cyanosis adversely affect well-being. In children, there are disturbances in the digestive system, in teenagers - heart palpitations, a feeling of heaviness in the heart area during muscle activity. Physical, mental and sexual development and growth of the child is delayed. Improperly long and thin limbs, especially the lower ones, are noticeable. Important signs are bluish fingers thickened in the form of drums. Complications of the defect - coma due to a decrease in the amount of oxygen in the blood, thrombosis, frequent pneumonia, infectious endocarditis, heart failure.

Summary: Pulmonary artery stenosis is often caused by stenosis of pulmonary valves, less often by sub- and supravulvar stenosis, stenosis of pulmonary artery branches.

Coarctation of the aorta is a narrowing that is often observed below the origin of the left subclavian artery from the aorta.

Aortic valve stenosis accounts for approximately 5% of all congenital heart disease in children. Valvular stenosis is common (about 80%), subvalvular and supravulvar variants of aortic stenosis are less common (20%). An anomaly in the structure of the aortic valve (bicuspidity) is one of the main congenital heart defects in adults.

CHD is a congenital heart defect - if the child has cyanosis or severe pallor, poor nutrition, frequent colds, intolerance to age-appropriate physical activity (quick fatigue during breastfeeding, active play, shortness of breath), one can doubt. even climbing the stairs once, etc.), increased heart volume, changes in heart sounds, the appearance of heart murmurs, changes in the pulse in the hands, weak or absent heartbeats. femoral artery, changes in arterial blood pressure, deformation of the chest, heart rhythm disorders, any pathological ECG changes, unusual changes detected in the chest X-ray, etc.

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